

Saint Mary's University
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
University Research Center

RESEARCH PROJECT

I. Title

Level of Knowledge and Awareness on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program among Grade 6 Pupils in Nueva Vizcaya

II. Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge and awareness of elementary pupils on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program. It also explored significant correlations between the two mentioned variables. Moreover, it determined the significant difference between these variables when the respondents are grouped by sex. This study used a quantitative approach particularly the descriptive-comparative and correlation type of research. The data were obtained through a Google form test on the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM. Frequency, percent distribution, mean, and standard deviation were computed to describe the level of knowledge and awareness. T-test for independent samples and Pearson-r were used in exploring if significant differences exist in the level of knowledge and awareness when the respondents are grouped by sex. Pearson-r correlation was used to reveal if the level of knowledge is significantly correlated to the level of awareness. T-test for paired samples was used to determine if a significant difference exists between knowledge and skills. The grade 6 pupils were knowledgeable and highly aware about DRRM. The level of knowledge and awareness of the pupils are the same regardless of their sex. Level of knowledge and awareness are not associated with each other. The awareness was higher than the knowledge of DRRM. The Grade 6 pupils perceived that they were aware but not all of them were able to answer the corresponding item in the knowledge test correctly.

The results of this study can be used as a basis for the improvement of the DRRM program and enhancement or revision of the curriculum particularly on the subjects integrated with DRRM. It can also be a basis in crafting Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials for DRRM awareness intended for Grade 6 pupils.

III. Research Agenda: Environmental Health

IV. Name of Proponents / Researchers

DR. MELANIE G. GURAT – lead researcher
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V. Mechanism Applied For: Mechanism D

VI. Rationale

Due to the urgency as a result of various calamities and disasters experienced by the Philippines, RA 10121 was enacted as a law. The Republic Act (RA) No. 10121 entitled "Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Act of 2010" mandates all national government agencies to institutionalize policies, structures, coordination mechanisms, and programs with continuing budget appropriation on disaster risk reduction and management from national to local levels.

In response to this law, the Department of Education (DepEd) created the Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (DRRMO) as stated in DO 50, s. 2011 to institutionalize the culture of safety at all levels, to systematize protection of education investments, and to ensure continued delivery of quality education services. The Science Education Institute of the Department of Science and Technology also positively responded through the conduct of intensive training on disaster awareness and preparedness to selected teachers and students all over the Philippines (DOST, 2018).

In the study of Gurat, Rivera, Antonio, and de Gracia (2019), the process, outcome, and impact of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program in two academic institutions were assessed. The impact was measured through the perceived effect of DRRM by senior high school students. The selected schools were limited only to the schools awarded with "Gawad KALASAG". Hence, the study only

captured an initial picture of the effect of disaster risk reduction and management program. In the same study, it was also explained that the Philippines is a country prone to natural disasters (Wingard & Brändlin, 2013; World Bank, 2015; Commission on Audit, 2014) due to the country's location along with two major tectonic plates of the world – the Eurasian and Pacific Plates. The Philippines is also exposed to typhoons, floods, drought, earthquakes, and volcanic eruptions. Nueva Vizcaya was also identified as one of the top ten provinces in the Philippines that are at risk of earthquakes (Center for Environmental Geomatics, 2005). Lagasca (2006) said that the province was categorized as earthquake- and landslide-prone especially since its mountainous areas are part of the active Digdig Faultline, which straddles Gabaldon, Nueva Ecija, and Benguet in the Cordilleras. Some of the recent catastrophes in Nueva Vizcaya include typhoon "Ompong". On September 26, 2018, the province was declared under a state of calamity because of the huge damages to infrastructures and agriculture brought by typhoon "Ompong" (Ebreo, 2018) and continuous rains that caused a creek to rise and cause massive flooding in Busilac, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya (Julio, 2018).

In her analysis of the K-12 curriculum of the Philippines, Merchant (2015) found that the students in the Philippines are receiving cumulative exposure to Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) in Grade 3 to 6 of the elementary level. However, they are not receiving the exposure across the curriculum because it is only integrated in science subjects, and not all grade levels acquire DRR education. She also found that based on the curriculum, multiple hazards are included in the K-12 program. Some of the lessons are how to remain safe and their proper clothes based on the weather conditions; effects of weather on the local community; and the importance of planning and preparing for safety. In Grade 5, pupils are taught to prepare emergency kits, recognize weather changes before, during, and after the typhoons and its effect on the community. In Grade 6, pupils are taught about earthquakes and volcanic eruptions. They learn how these hazards affect the earth and the appropriate measures to take before, during, and after the occurrence of earthquakes and/or volcanic eruptions. Local and community hazards are included in the curriculum as discussions and used as examples in several grade levels focusing on the natural hazards of earthquakes, volcanoes, tsunamis, and typhoons, which all affect the Philippines. Despite these findings, this cannot change the fact that the Philippines was considered as one of the five countries considered to be a very high-level risk as identified in the Index for Risk Management (INFORM).

The future of disaster preparedness and response is dependent on the next generation's knowledge and inclusion in the disaster process. According to Lekies and Wells (2006), people are fixed on a particular trajectory toward an outcome, and they will stay on this path unless a turning point occurs that sets them on a different trajectory. Accordingly, children need to be set on a trajectory that empowers them to protect themselves. There are currently many resources out there to assist in teaching children what to do; however, that information does not always reach them. If children continue to lack understanding and the ability to respond to a disaster effectively, then how can they be expected to be able to do so when they are adults who are in charge of making important decisions for their families and/or communities? A major challenge facing society today is insufficient knowledge being dispersed to children regarding preparation for a disaster and knowing how to respond when a disaster does strike. How can they be set on a trajectory that enables them to take charge of their safety in a time of disaster? To answer this question, the importance of being prepared, the role of children, and current preparedness resources need to be considered (Merchant, 2015) especially that the children are not spared from disasters and therefore be educated as early as basic education to keep them away from the ravages of disasters.

With these, it was deemed necessary to conduct a study that will evaluate the level of knowledge and awareness of Grade 5 and 6 pupils in Nueva Vizcaya. This study will help determine what could be improved in the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program to promote the safety of elementary level pupils of basic education. This will also serve as a basis for constructing Information Education and Communication (IEC) Materials.

VII. Statement of the Problems

This study determined the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM among Grade 6 Pupils in Nueva Vizcaya.

Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the pupils' level of knowledge on DRRM?
2. What is the pupils' level of awareness on DRRM?
3. Is there a significant difference in the mean ratings of the level of knowledge when the pupils are grouped by their sex?

4. Is there a significant difference in the mean ratings of the level of awareness when the pupils are grouped by their sex?
5. Is there a significant correlation between the mean scores on the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM?
6. Is there a significant difference in the mean ratings of the level of knowledge and skills on DRRM?

VIII. Statement of Null Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM when grouped by sex.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the level of knowledge on DRRM when grouped by sex.
3. There is no significant correlation between the mean ratings of the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the level of knowledge and skills on DRRM.

IX. Conceptual Framework

Disaster Risk Reduction in education is aimed at the protection of learners and education workers. It aimed for educational continuity in the face of expected hazards, safeguarding education sector investments, and strengthening climate-smart disaster resilience through education towards safe learning facilities, school disaster management, school disaster management, and risk reduction and resilience education. Failure of the education system to do these can lose the promise of education forever (UNESCO, UNICEF, & Save the Children). Due to the urgency as a result of various calamities and disasters experienced by the Philippines, RA 10121 was enacted as a law and in response to this law, the Department of Education (DepEd) created the Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (DRRMO) as stated in DO 50, s. 2011 to institutionalize the culture of safety at all levels, to systematize protection of education investments, and to ensure continued delivery of quality education services. Gurat, Rivera, Antonio, and de Gracia (2019) assessed the impact of DRRM through the perceived effect of DRRM by senior high school students. Their study only captured an initial picture of the effect of disaster risk reduction and management program. Merchant (2015) said that the major challenge facing society today is insufficient knowledge being dispersed to children regarding their preparation and response when a disaster strike.

This study was guided by the research paradigm shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows the research paradigm of the study. The main variables of the study are the level of knowledge and level of awareness on DRRM. These two variables are connected with a double-headed arrow indicating that the significant correlation of these variables was explored. The profile variable that was considered is contained in the first box, the sex. The arrow from this box is towards the main variables indicating that the study determined if a significant difference exists when the pupils are grouped by their profile variable. The result will be towards Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials. This is connected with a broken arrow, which means that this study will serve as a guide for the researchers to construct IEC materials for DRRM awareness and will be tested in phase 3 of the research.

IX. Scope and Delimitation

This study focused on the determination of the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM. This study determined if significant differences between the mean ratings on the level of knowledge and awareness of the pupils when grouped by the selected profile variable of the respondents which was sex. This study explored if there is a significant correlation between the level of knowledge and awareness.

The respondents of the study were limited to Grade 6 only. The study was conducted at Solano East Elementary School. The level of knowledge and awareness was limited to the result obtained from the adopted test questionnaire and a researcher-made survey questionnaire.

X. Significance of the Study

Department of Education. They will be guided on how to improve the DRRM program in the academic institutions particularly at the elementary level in the whole division of Nueva Vizcaya. The result can also be a basis for the improvement of the curriculum. In particular, it will help them realize the strengths and weaknesses of the activities conducted in line with disaster risk reduction and management program. They will also be informed about the results of the effectiveness of the program.

School Administrators. The result of this study can help the school administrators improve the DRRM both the program and the curriculum at the school level. This will serve as a basis for them to come up with alternative plans in achieving the objectives of the program.

DRRM school coordinators. They will be guided on the activities to be included in their action plan. They will also be guided on the extent of training the elementary pupils on DRRM.

Teachers. They will be guided on the extent of assistance to the pupils of Grade 5 and Grade 6 during a disaster. This study will prompt the teacher on what teaching strategies to use to prepare their pupils for disasters. They will also know how well they taught their pupils and how well the pupils learned from their teachings on DRRM.

Parents. The information that they will get from the results of the study can prompt them on what to do to secure the safety of their children during disasters.

Pupils. They will be given proper training and guidance concerning the DRRM objectives.

XI. Definition of Terms

Disaster Risk Reduction Management. This refers to the program of academic institutions per Republic Act 10121, an act strengthening the Philippine disaster risk reduction and management system.

Level of knowledge on DRRM. This refers to the extent of understanding of the pupils on DRRM. It is described as not knowledgeable, slightly knowledgeable, moderately knowledgeable, knowledgeable, and highly knowledgeable. The knowledge on DRRM was based on the test on DRRM which will be a multiple choice type of test.

Level of awareness of DRRM. This pertains to how well the pupils are familiar with the DRRM. It is described as not aware, slightly aware, moderately aware, aware, and highly aware. The scores were based on the number of checks in positive items (stating correct information about DRRM) and the number of "x" marks on negative items (about items that are not correct). The level of awareness was measured using a checklist.

XII. Review of Related Literature and Studies

A. Disaster Risk Reduction Management in the Philippines

The Philippines is vulnerable to natural hazards and these are attributed to its geographic position in Southeast Asia. Natural disasters which include typhoons, earthquakes, floods, volcanic eruptions, landslides, and fires affect the country. Because it is one of the most geologically active areas, it is nicknamed "The Ring of Fire" (Philippines: Disaster Management Reference Handbook, 2018) and thus can experience volcanic eruptions and tsunamis. Rising sea levels are also a direct threat to approximately 70 percent of the Philippine population, which has forced many to relocate as a result. Climate change has also increased the severity and frequency of natural disasters in the country.

According to Montenegro (2015), a total of 274 disasters were recorded in the Philippines from 1995 to 2015, trailing the United States (472), China (441), and India (288).

The ASEAN Safe Schools Initiative (ASSI, 2015) narrates the following actions of the government about disaster risk management in the Philippines as applied in schools.

In the year 2007, disaster risk reduction was integrated into both formal and non-formal curricula in the Philippines as outlined through DepEd Order No. 55, s. which is about prioritizing the mainstreaming of disaster risk reduction management in the school system. DO No. 55 directs the

utilization of DepEd's Disaster Risk Reduction Resource Manual as a guide for mainstreaming disaster risk reduction concepts in primary and secondary school curricula and developing multimedia modules on disaster preparedness. The science and social science subjects of grades 6 and 7 were identified for the integration of disaster risk reduction. Experts from the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) and Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) developed, tested, and validated lesson exemplars together with the teacher and student modules. The materials for printing were reviewed and approved by The Instructional Materials Council-Secretariat and the National DRRM Council. A Disaster Risk Reduction Resource Manual was also developed for school administrators, principals, supervisors, and teachers on the implementation of disaster risk reduction projects.

In the year 2010, the Republic Act 10121 (or the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010) was passed, and DepEd created the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (DRRMO) as the vital point in planning, implementing, coordinating, and monitoring activities related to disaster risk reduction, education in emergencies and climate change adaptation. Their roles included initiating and coordinating activities with government agencies and civil society organizations, and serving as the clearinghouse for all school safety resources including production and issuance of teaching and learning materials, and distribution of school kits. A Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Focal Point for each region and division were assigned with the creation of DRRMO.

According to Miasco (2017), Section 14 of RA 10121 of 2010 requires DepEd, CHED, and TESDA to integrate disaster risk education in school curricula. The law stated that DepEd and CHED have an important role to play in the country's approach to DRRM. It mandates local DRRM bodies to "encourage community, specifically the youth, participation in disaster risk reduction and management activities, such as organizing quick response groups, particularly in identified disaster-prone areas, as well as the inclusion of disaster risk reduction and management programs as part of youth programs and projects".

In the year 2013, there was a change in the Philippine Basic Education System as it widely adopted the K-12 Program that covers kindergarten and 12 years of basic education. Together with the change, entry points for the integration of disaster risk reduction were identified. Disaster risk reduction was integrated into the curriculum more comprehensively in the health, science, and social science subjects for grades 1-10 and Earth science for grades 11-12.

In the year 2015, the DRRMO became DRRM Service. It was granted identical authority with other offices in DepEd. The following are key policies related to school safety that they have issued:

- Disaster Preparedness Measures for Schools (DO 83, s. 2011)
- Guidelines on the Use of the Quick Response Fund (DM 104, s. 2011) – that can be used by disaster-affected schools
- Enforcement of support to implement grant calamity loans to teaching and non-teaching staff in areas affected by calamities (DO 10, s. 2011)
- Quarterly conduct of the National School-based Earthquake and Fire Drills (DO 48, s. 2012)
- Continuing Fire Safety and Awareness Program (FSAP) in Schools (DO 72, s. 2012)
- Integration of disaster risk reduction in the data collection forms incorporated in the Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS) (DO 23, s. 2014)
- Guidelines on Student-Led School Watching and Hazard Mapping (DO 23, s. 2015)
- Promoting Family Earthquake Preparedness to all elementary and secondary schools with instruction and guidance (DO 27, s. 2015)
- Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Basic Education Framework (DO 37, s. 2015)

The Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in the Basic Education Framework implements the Global Framework for Comprehensive School Safety. It guides in the following:

- The inclusion of DRRM in the school, division, and regional education development plans.
- The implementation of DRRM for education practitioners' and partners' planning and programming at all levels.
- Defining the agency's preparedness, response, recovery, and rehabilitation initiatives concerning hazards affecting school operations.
- Serving as a mechanism for engaging partners and aligning their thrust to DepEd priorities.
- Guiding collaboration with private schools.

Accordingly, different organizations made efforts on disaster risk reduction; some of which included the following:

- The UNICEF integrated disaster risk reduction in the K12 curriculum by training 844 kindergarten to grade 3 teachers, school principals, and supervisors, on child development principles and learner-centered approaches.
- Save the Children, in collaboration with DepEd and with support from the United States Agency for International Development, implemented a Mainstreaming Disaster Risk Reduction in the School System initiative as early as 2011 by training at least 4,000 students, and 300 public secondary school teachers and DepEd officials on mainstreaming disaster risk reduction in the school system. They also organized the National Congress on School Disaster Risk Reduction that was participated by over 200 students, school officials, government agencies representatives, NGOs, and development partners from all 17 regions of the country to share and learn school safety best practices in the year 2012.
- SEEDS Asia with the Hyogo Prefectural Board of Education in Japan and the Japan International Cooperation Agency partnered with DepEd in the integration of disaster risk reduction in the curriculum. They called the project Capacity Building on Disaster Risk Reduction Education through Cooperation with Local Community in Cebu Province which started in November 2014. Their activities included creating a system to promote disaster risk reduction education at DepEd Region 7 Office, training DepEd officials and teachers, establishing two model schools, and replicating the models to seven schools in Cebu Province.

According to Lopez, Echavez, Magallen, and Sales (2018), risk reduction is recognized as vital for building a more equitable future and for reducing the severity of losses during disasters. They expounded that effective risk reduction occurs when there is cooperation between sectors of society, and there is an existing disaster preparedness program in place.

B. Knowledge and Awareness of Disasters

Disaster is a natural or human-caused hazard that causes a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society involving widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses and impacts, which exceeds the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources (UNISDR) (Ahmad, Anees, Geelani, Nusrat, Jan, & Zargar, 2017). There is a concern over natural disasters globally. Disasters like floods, earthquakes, and fires pose serious threats to people and may even result in loss of life and property. Apart from causing deaths and severe ill health, disasters also lead to large-scale displacement, injuries, epidemics, and substantial economic losses to the communities (Marskole, Mishra, Kumar, Gaur, Aharwar, Patidar, & Shejwar, 2018).

Disaster education, which includes education on disaster risks, mitigation, and preparedness strategies, is one approach to reducing the negative consequences of disasters (Smith, 1993; Mulyasari et al., 2011). Ahmad et al. (2017) highlight the need for disaster safety education. There is a need to increase the knowledge and awareness of people regarding natural and man-made disasters to make them able to cope up with their adverse effects. Essential preparedness planning and mitigation are needed to minimize the threat of damage to life and property (Wanjala & Onyango, 2018).

Merchant (2015) emphasizes that education is especially important for more vulnerable populations such as children. She stated that the most efficient way to reach as many children as possible is within the education system. She added that teaching children how to prepare for and respond to a disaster can be extremely beneficial, as having awareness can help to reduce some of the emotional and psychological risks. She expounded that through everyday socialization, children can take what they learn in the classroom and bring it home to share with their family and friends. She considers this type of networking beneficial to the community by expanding the breadth of knowledge and awareness of DRR practices. She considers that it also increases the number of people in the community who can protect themselves and help in the period after a disaster strikes. She thinks that to accomplish this goal, DRR education must be implemented in the school curricula around the world.

Gerdan (2014) considers that in disaster-prone countries, preparedness is an important factor in disaster mitigation. He said that it is possible to increase the capacity to cope with the disasters, which show variations in terms of their development periods and times and mostly involve uncertainty, by raising the awareness of all components, all individuals and communities in line with this common cause. He emphasizes that the level of education is an important factor in reducing disaster damages. In his study, he determined the levels of disaster awareness and attitude and the individual priorities of the personnel and the students at the Umuttepe Campus of Kocaeli University. He found that students in the Department of Engineering have the highest awareness level of all. Most of these students are from the

Departments of Geology and Geophysics and have the privilege of taking courses related to disasters. His results support the world's science-based developments and emphasize that education and training in disaster awareness in formal education are very important.

Hoffmann and Muttarak (2017) posit that education raises disaster preparedness only for those households that have not been affected by a disaster in the past. They consider that education improves abstract reasoning and anticipation skills such that the better educated undertake preventive measures without needing to first experience the harmful event and then learn later.

The behaviors of individuals on the issue of being able to cope with disasters are directly proportional to their level of preparedness and awareness (Pinar, 2017).

Some studies that determine the knowledge or awareness of some groups of people include the following.

Marskole et al. (2018) assessed the extent of awareness about disasters and their management among school-going children. They found that the extent of knowledge is not yet satisfactory and there is a severe need of providing knowledge to the school children. They suggested that disaster management can be compulsorily included in the academic curriculum of all the students and effective, purposeful training and awareness programs are to be timely conducted.

El-Hosany and Ghonem (2017) assessed the knowledge and awareness of students, employees, and staff members about the major components of disaster preparedness before and after implementation of an educational program, to determine the expectations of faculty of nursing members about disaster management guidelines and to examine the reliability and content validity of proposed disaster management guidelines. The study showed a significantly higher level of awareness and knowledge among employees and teaching staff compared to students but they all had insufficient knowledge and awareness before the implementation of the educational program. Their knowledge and awareness significantly increased after the educational program regarding major components of disaster preparedness guidelines. The insufficient knowledge and awareness of the faculty of nursing members before the implementation of the educational program significantly improved after the application of the program.

Sujarwo, Noorhamdani, and Fathoni (2018) considered knowledge and attitudes as key factors that must be taken into account in efforts to increase student preparedness to reduce the risk of a tsunami disaster. They found out that there was a significant influence between knowledge and attitude towards the preparedness of students in DRR in Sipora, Mentawai Islands district.

Corpuz (2019) conducted a study that involved thirty (30) private and public schools in Biñan City, Laguna. Findings showed that the schools have a very high level of implementation of disaster risk management practices for earthquakes. The schools have a high level of implementation of disaster risk management practices for both fires and floods. The schools have a high level of readiness for disasters. Private schools have a higher level of implementation of disaster risk management practices for floods. Private schools have a higher level of readiness for disasters than public schools. The higher the schools' level of implementation of disaster risk management practices for earthquakes, fires, and floods is, the higher is their level of readiness for disasters.

Hoffmann and Muttarak (2017) conducted a study that aimed at understanding the role of education in promoting disaster preparedness. The study focused on determinants of personal disaster preparedness and it investigated pathways through which education enhances the preparedness and the interplay between education and experience in shaping preparedness actions. They found that formal education raises the propensity to prepare against disasters. They found that the effect of education on disaster preparedness is mainly mediated through social capital and disaster risk perception in Thailand whereas there is no evidence that education is mediated through observable channels in the Philippines. They suggest that the underlying mechanisms explaining the education effects are highly context-specific. Their study provides solid empirical evidence showing positive externalities of education in disaster risk reduction.

Tuladhar, Yatabe, Dahal, and Bhandary (2014) explored the benefits of existing education programs of DRR in Nepal. They found that initiatives taken for disaster education in Nepal are not enough and a major challenge for DRR in a school community for a country like Nepal is implementing methods, especially at the individual level. Also, the study stated that disaster education should not only be confined within the school students, but it must also be promoted to families and communities, which is very essential to elaborate knowledge of DRR and to contribute to a disaster safe society in the country.

Vicerra, Salvador, and Capili (2018) conducted a study which aimed to appraise such program on university students regarding self-perceived knowledge of disaster preparedness, confidence on actual preparedness, and engaging performing knowledge to action. They found out that belief in being

prepared and knowing what to do was significantly different for the hypothetical earthquake scenario, but was not observed for the typhoon scenario. They also found out that complacency is absent regarding typhoons because people in their age group residing in Marikina City, as well as those living in adjacent areas, have experienced it in recent years but earthquakes bring uncertainty.

Ahmad et al. (2017) studied the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding disaster preparedness of college students studying in district Ganderbal of Kashmir Valley. Their results showed that there is a general lack of information among students regarding disaster awareness and preparedness. They found that level of practice was largely negative with acceptable knowledge and positive attitude regarding disaster preparedness among the college students. They stated that students can be proving useful workforce in a disaster situation and that college students need to know basic strategies carried out in a disaster.

Mamogale (2009) determined the extent to which disaster preparedness was achieved by learners and educators in schools located in Soshanguve North, Gauteng Province, South Africa by sourcing data from principals, educators, learners, and school safety committees. They found that educators were not trained in disaster management and that learners tended to be the ones who were aware of disaster preparedness in this study when their knowledge about hazards and disasters acquired at school was assessed.

Mamon, Suba, and Lakip Son Jr. (2017) conducted a study to assess the disaster-related knowledge, preparedness and readiness, adaptation, awareness, and risk perception of 120 Grade 11 students of a senior high school in Las Piñas City. They found that there was a high percentage of students who understood some disaster-related concepts and ideas. Grade 11 students are ready, prepared, adapted, and aware of the risks inflicted by disasters, but students were found to have low-disaster risk perception. Senior high school students have high levels of disaster-related knowledge, preparedness and readiness, adaptation, and awareness. Results showed that senior high school students have high levels of disaster-related knowledge, preparedness and readiness, adaptation, and awareness attributed to the integration of disaster education in the senior high school science curriculum.

Pinar (2017) determined the basic disaster consciousness and awareness level of secondary school students. This study concluded that secondary students classified the disaster concept as a phenomenon related only to natural factors, failed to identify the human factors causing the disaster, classified the disaster types as natural disasters and failed to classify the dimension of the disasters, lacked sufficient knowledge in disaster preparedness as well as predictions with regards to the disaster types they may face in their regions. Students also considered the level of development of the country as a determining factor in disaster management.

Padernal and Borja (2016) determined the level of awareness on disaster risk reduction issues on natural hazards among the public junior high school students of Surigao City. The public junior high school students are generally aware of disaster risk reduction issues associated with natural hazards. There is a significant difference in the level of awareness when the respondents were grouped according to sex on issues about the earthquake, typhoon, landslide, volcanic eruption, and flood. They arrived at the following conclusions: The K-12 curriculum of the Department of Education and symposia on disaster awareness of the National Disaster Risk Reduction Management Council of Surigao City are effective in disseminating information concerning disaster risk reduction to junior high school students. Females are more vigilant than males on disaster risk reduction issues on earthquake, typhoon, landslides, volcanic eruptions, and floods because they are more sensitive about the environmental issues which are attributed to the gender role that they play in the society. Students are more aware of how to reduce the risk of natural hazards that often occur in Surigao City which is the typhoon as compared to other calamities.

Lopez, Echavez, Magallen, and Sales (2018) determined the level of compliance with the school risk reduction and disaster preparedness program among the public secondary schools in the District of Buenavista, Bohol, Philippines. Their study determined compliance in the aspects of safe learning facilities, school disaster management, and disaster risk reduction in education. It found that schools had a good compliance level on disaster preparedness. But some problems were encountered such as inadequate training materials and lack of training among the school disaster risk reduction management teams.

Synthesis

Natural disasters which include typhoons, earthquakes, floods, volcanic eruptions, landslides, and fires can affect the Philippines because of its geographic location. These can cause 'a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society involving widespread human, material,

economic or environmental losses and impacts, which exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources' (UNISDR in Ahmad et al., 2017). This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge and awareness on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program. It also explored significant correlations between the two mentioned variables. Moreover, it determined the significant difference between these variables when grouped by sex and grade level.

All studies cited were conducted in the school and dealt with disasters (awareness, knowledge, or preparedness). The research works of Marskole et al. (2018), Gerdan (2014), and Pinar (2017) dealt with awareness of disasters while the works of Vicerra et al. (2018) and Ahmad et al. (2017) included knowledge of disasters. El-Hosany and Ghonem (2017) considered both knowledge and awareness about the major components of disaster preparedness before and after implementation of an educational program

Similar to the study of Marskole et al. (2018), this study involved elementary school children. However, this study is different from Sujarwo et al. (2018) because it did not determine the influence between knowledge and attitude towards preparedness for disasters. This study is unlike the research of Vicerra et al. (2018) because it did not appraise confidence on actual preparedness and engaging performing knowledge to action. Unlike the study of Corpuz (2019), the level of implementation of disaster risk management practices for disasters for both public and private schools was not considered. Moreover, this study did not identify the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of college students regarding disaster preparedness just like the study of Ahmad et al. (2017) and it did not determine the extent to which disaster preparedness was achieved by learners and educators in schools as studied by Mamogale (2009).

XIII. Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative approach particularly descriptive-comparative and correlational type. This study is descriptive for it described the level of knowledge and awareness of Grade 6 pupils on DRRM. This study explored the significant differences in the levels of knowledge and awareness of the pupils when grouped by sex and significant correlations between these two variables. Hence, this is comparative and correlational respectively.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Solano East Elementary School. It is a public school located at Espino St., Brgy. Roxas, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. A public elementary school was considered in the study because it is expected that teachers face greater responsibilities in this type of school especially in times of disaster where it is possible that they might not control their pupils.

Respondents of the Study

The selected Grade 6 pupils from the randomly selected schools in Nueva Vizcaya were the respondents of the study. Grades 6 pupils were considered because at this stage, the pupils are encouraged and expected to be more independent and to require less guidance and support from adults. There were eighteen (46.2%) male pupils and twenty-one (53.8%) female pupils.

Research Instruments

Knowledge Test on DRRM. This test measures the level of knowledge of the Grade 6 pupils on DRRM. This was adopted from the test found in the textbook "Teaching Disaster Risk Reduction with Interactive Methods" developed by Ratiani et al. (2011). The instrument was validated by the officer in charge of DRRM of Division Office of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

Survey on Awareness on DRRM. The test is a dichotomous type of questionnaire answerable by Yes or No. The items were a researcher-made questionnaire which is aligned from the adopted test from the textbook developed by Ratiani et al. (2011).

Informed consent form. This form was given to the parents/guardian of the pupils to inform them that their children will be given a test on the level of knowledge and survey questionnaire in the awareness and that the data will be used in this study. Permission to allow their children was asked from the parents/guardians.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedures were followed to gather pertinent data needed in the study.

1. As soon as this study was approved, the researchers finalized the questionnaire.
2. Communication letters were forwarded to the Department of Education, Division of Nueva Vizcaya for the request to conduct the study and to the principal of the selected school.
3. As soon as the request was granted, a schedule was set for data gathering. However, the data was not retrieved due to the declaration of Enhanced Community Quarantine due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Hence, there was a change of plan in the data gathering procedure.
4. The research instrument was encoded to Google form and the assistance of the DepEd research specialist was sought.
5. The Google form was sent to the possible pupils. However, due to the connectivity and permission letter to the parents to allow their children, the data gathered were very limited. The original Grade 5 and Grade 6 pupils were trimmed down to Grade 6 only and no questionnaire from the private institution was retrieved.
6. The data obtained were analyzed and interpreted.

Data Analysis

The scores of the pupils on the test on DRRM were converted to percent score, using the formula

$$\%Score = \frac{X}{Perfect\ Score}$$

where X is the number of correct answers. The level of knowledge was described using the scale found in Table 1.

Table 1. Scale for Interpretation

%Score	Level of Knowledge	Level of Awareness
0 – 19.49	The respondent is not knowledgeable.	The respondent is not aware of it.
19.50 – 39.49	The respondent is slightly knowledgeable.	The respondent is slightly aware.
39.50 – 59.49	The respondent is moderately knowledgeable.	The respondent is moderately aware.
59.50 – 79.49	The respondent is knowledgeable.	The respondent is aware.
79.50 – 100	The respondent is highly knowledgeable.	The respondent is highly aware.

The summary of the level of knowledge was described through frequency and percent distribution. Mean and standard deviation were also computed to describe the level of knowledge on DRRM of Grade 6 pupils.

The number of the “yes” responses on the awareness questionnaire on DRRM of Grade 6 pupils was converted to a percent score. The interpretation was based on the scale in Table 1.

T-test for independent samples was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the mean ratings on the level of knowledge and awareness of the pupils when grouped by sex.

Pearson-r was computed to determine if there is a significant correlation between the mean ratings on the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM.

Paired-Sample t-test was used to determine if a significant difference exists between the knowledge and skills of DRRM.

Result and Discussion

Section 1. Level of knowledge on DRRM of the pupils

Table 2 shows the distribution of the level of knowledge on DRRM of Grade 6 pupils.

Table 2. Frequency Count and Percent of the Level of Knowledge on DRRM of Grade 6 Pupils

Level of Knowledge	Frequency	Percent
Slightly Knowledgeable	2	5.1
Moderately Knowledgeable	1	2.6
Knowledgeable	17	43.6
Highly Knowledgeable	19	48.7
Total	39	100.0

Mean: 75.10 (Knowledgeable) SD: 14.037

As shown in Table 2, most of the grade 6 pupils were knowledgeable (43.6%) or highly knowledgeable (48.7%) on DRRM. A few of them were slightly knowledgeable (5.1 %) or moderately knowledgeable (2.6%) on DRRM. The average knowledge of the Grade 6 pupils was 75.10, indicating that they were knowledgeable.

The above result means that the Grade 6 pupils were able to learn from the intervention conducted by their teachers. It also indicates that the school is compliant with the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program. This means the DRRM was integrated into their curriculum not only through their subject but also through the drills being conducted nationally such as the quarterly conduct of the National School-based Earthquake and Fire Drills (DO 48, s. 2012). This was supported by Corpuz (2019) who found that schools have a high level of implementation of DRRM. The result on the level of knowledge is similar to the study of El-Hosany and Ghonem (2017) who found an improved level of awareness and knowledge. However, in their study, an intervention was conducted and the employees and staff members were included in the study. Mamon et al. (2017) also obtained a favorable result on understanding some disaster-related concepts and ideas. But their respondents were Grade 11 students. The result is different from the findings of Marskole et al. (2018) who found that the extent of knowledge is not satisfactory.

Section 2. The level of awareness on DRRM of the pupils

Table 3 shows the distribution of the level of awareness on DRRM of Grade 6 pupils.

Table 3. Frequency Count and Percent of the Level of Awareness on DRRM of Grade 6 Pupils

Level of Awareness	Frequency	Percent
Slightly Aware	1	2.6
Moderately Aware	3	7.7
Aware	6	15.4
Highly Aware	29	74.4
Total	39	100.0

Mean: 85.86 (Highly Aware), SD: 17.862

As shown in Table 3, majority of the Grade 6 pupils were highly aware (74.4%) of DRRM. Some were aware (15.4%), moderately aware (7.7%), and slightly aware (2.6%). The average awareness of the Grade 6 pupils was described as "Highly Aware" with a mean of 85.86.

Grade 6 pupils must be highly aware of the DRRM not because it is part of their curriculum but most especially because of the threats the disasters can cause human beings (Marskole et al., 2018).

Table 4 shows the frequency and percent of the responses of the pupils in each item of the questionnaire on awareness on DRRM.

Table 4. Frequency Count and Percent of the Responses

Statements	YES		NO	
	f	%	f	%
1. I am aware of what the DRRM Program is all about.	32	82.05	7	17.95
2. I am aware of the contents of emergency kit/bag.	36	92.31	3	7.69
3. I am aware where the evacuation center is in case of emergency.	31	79.49	8	20.51
4. I am aware of the forms of disaster.	35	89.74	4	10.26
5. I am aware that continuous rain is not dangerous.*	17	43.59	22	56.41
6. I am aware of the rules of action before an earthquake.	37	94.87	2	5.13
7. I am aware what to do during an earthquake.	39	100.00	0	0.00
8. I am aware of the things that should not be done during earthquake.	37	94.87	2	5.13
9. I am aware of what to do if I am inside a building during an earthquake.	36	92.31	3	7.69
10. I am aware of the safest place on the street during an earthquake.	35	89.74	4	10.26
11. I am aware of the safest place in the building during an earthquake.	32	82.05	7	17.95
12. I am aware of the things that need to be fixed inside the classroom before an earthquake.	34	87.18	5	12.82
13. I am aware of the reasons for the flood.	38	97.44	1	2.56
14. I am aware of what to do during flood.	38	97.44	1	2.56
15. I am aware of what to do before flood.	35	89.74	4	10.26

Statements	YES		NO	
	f	%	f	%
16. I am aware of what to do after flood.	38	97.44	1	2.56
17. I am aware of what to do to avoid floods.	34	87.18	5	12.82
18. I am aware of what to do if I am on a roof or higher ground during a flood.	31	79.49	8	20.51
19. I am aware of what to do if my clothes are on fire.	33	84.62	6	15.38
20. I am aware of what I should do in the building during a fire.	28	71.79	11	28.21
21. I am aware how to put out a small fire.	37	94.87	2	5.13
22. I am aware how to leave a building in smoke.	31	79.49	8	20.51
23. I am aware of the rules of lighting a fire in the forest.	32	82.05	7	17.95
24. I am aware of what to do to avoid a landslide.	30	76.92	9	23.08
25. I am aware of what to do at home during a landslide.	29	74.36	10	25.64
26. I am aware about the characteristics of a landslide.	29	74.36	10	25.64
27. I am aware of what to do during a thunderstorm.	37	94.87	2	5.13
28. I am aware of what to do if a thunderstorm occurs while in an open space outdoors.	29	74.36	10	25.64
29. I am aware of what to do if I am in a building during a strong wind.	33	84.62	6	15.38
30. I am aware how I would act if I am outside during a strong wind.	34	87.18	5	12.82

*negative item

The result reveals that majority of the Grade 6 pupils claimed that they were aware of basic information about DRRM such as what DRRM Program is all about (82.05%); the content of emergency kit (92.31%); the evacuation center (79.76%); forms of disasters (89.74%); and that continuous rain is dangerous (56.41%). With regards to earthquakes, they also claimed that they were aware of the rules of action (94.87%), what to do (100%), the things that should not be done (94.87%); what to do if inside a building (92.31%); the safest place on street (89.74%); the safest place in the building (82.05%); and what needs to be fixed inside the classroom (87.18%). In terms of floods, they claimed that they were aware of the reasons for the calamity (97.44%), what to do during (97.44%), before (89.74%) flood, and after (97.44%). They were also aware of what to do to avoid floods (87.18%), and what to do if they were on a roof or higher ground during a flood (79.79%). They were also aware of DRRM in a fire such as what to do if their clothes are on fire (84.62%), in the building (71.79%), to put out a small fire (94.87%), to leave a building in smoke (79.49%), and rules of lightning fire in the forest (82.05%). They were also aware of the landslides such as what to do to avoid it (76.92%), what to do at home (74.36%), and the characteristics of landslides (74.36%). The pupils were also aware of what to do during a thunderstorm (94.87%), what to do while in open space (74.36%), during strong wind in a building (84.62%) or outside (87.18%).

Moreover, the result shows that the Grade 6 pupils were aware of the different disasters and the DRRM in the different forms of disaster such as earthquake, flood, fire, landslide, thunderstorm, and strong wind. The same result was obtained by Gerdan (2014) who conducted a similar study in Umuttepe Campus of Koraeli University.

Section 3. Significant difference between the mean ratings of the level of knowledge of the pupils when grouped by their sex

Table 5 shows the result of the t-test for independent samples to find if a significant difference exists between the levels of knowledge of the pupils on DRRM when grouped by their sex.

Table 5. Significant Difference Between the Mean Ratings of the Level of Knowledge of the Pupils when Grouped by their Sex

Sex	N	Mean	Level	Std. Deviation	Test Statistic
Male	18	77.78	Knowledgeable	10.109	t(37) = 1.105, p = .276
Female	21	72.81	Knowledgeable	16.600	

As gleaned in Table 5, the mean rating of the level of knowledge of the male pupils (77.78) was higher than female pupils (72.81). However, the t-test for independent sample result reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge of the male and female pupils. This is supported by the mean range 59.50-79.49%, which means that both male and female pupils were knowledgeable on DRRM.

Section 4. Significant difference between the mean ratings of the level of awareness when the pupils are grouped by the pupil's sex

Table 6 shows the result of the t-test for independent samples to find if a significant difference exists between the levels of awareness of the pupils on DRRM when grouped by their sex.

Table 6. Significant Difference Between the Mean Rating of the Level of Awareness of the Pupils when Grouped by their Sex

Sex	N	Mean	Level of Awareness	Std. Deviation	Test-statistic
Male	18	78.89	Aware	22.90	t(25.802) = -1.931, p = .064
Female	21	91.63	Highly Aware	12.85	

As shown in Table 6, the mean rating of the level of awareness on DRRM of the female pupils (91.63) was higher than the mean rating of the male pupils (78.89). The qualitative description of the level of awareness of female pupils was "highly aware" while the male pupils were "aware". However, the t-test for independent samples did not support the findings with a result of $t(28.802) = -1.931, p = 0.064$. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female pupils. This also means that the level of awareness of the pupils was the same regardless of their sex.

Section 5. Significant Correlation Between the Scores of the Level of Knowledge and Awareness on DRRM

Table 7 displays the Pearson-r correlation result between the score in knowledge and skills in DRRM.

Table 7. Correlation between the Scores of the Level of Knowledge and Awareness on DRRM

		Score in awareness
Score in knowledge	Pearson Correlation	-.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.994
	N	39

The Pearson-r result ($r = -0.12$) is very close to zero, indicating that there was a very weak correlation between the score and awareness. This is negligible that the p-value also resulted in 0.994 showing that this very weak correlation is not significant. The knowledge and awareness were not associated with each other. The details were explored through the frequency count and percent of the responses of the pupils whether they claimed that they were aware and they got a correct answer, they were not aware but they got a correct answer in the knowledge test, or they claimed that they were aware but they did not get a correct answer. This is shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Frequency and Count Percent of Responses in the Awareness Questionnaire and Knowledge Test

Items	Aware and Knowledgeable		Not Aware but Knowledgeable		Aware but not Knowledgeable	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. what DRRM Program is all about	20	51.28	3	7.7	12	30.8
2. contents of emergency kit/bag	36	92.31	3	7.7	0	0
3. where the evacuation center is in case of emergency	16	41.03	2	5.1	15	38.5
4. forms of disaster	34	87.18	4	10.3	1	2.6
5. consequences of continuous rain	21	53.85	0	0	1	2.6
6. rules of action before an earthquake	29	74.36	2	5.1	8	20.5
7. what to do during an earthquake	31	79.49	0	0	8	20.5
8. things that should be done during an earthquake	32	82.05	1	2.6	5	12.8
9. what to do if inside a building during an earthquake	28	71.79	2	5.1	8	20.5
10. safest place on the street during an earthquake	33	84.62	4	10.3	2	5.1
11. safest place in the building during an earthquake.	31	79.49	7	17.9	1	2.6
12. things that need to be fixed inside the	22	56.41	5	12.8	12	30.8

Items	Aware and Knowledgeable		Not Aware but Knowledgeable		Aware but not Knowledgeable	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
classroom before an earthquake						
13. reasons for a flood	36	92.31	1	2.6	2	5.1
14. what to do during a flood	31	79.49	1	2.6	7	17.9
15. what to do before a flood	22	56.41	4	10.3	13	33.3
16. what to do after a flood	31	79.49	1	2.3	7	17.9
17. what to do to avoid floods	27	69.23	5	12.8	7	17.9
18. what to do if on a roof or higher ground during a flood	27	69.23	8	20.5	4	10.3
19. what to do if clothes are on fire	31	79.49	5	12.8	2	5.1
20. what should be done in a building during a fire	16	41.03	6	15.4	12	30.8
21. how to put out a small fire	6	15.38	0	0	31	79.5
22. how to leave a building in smoke	29	74.36	8	20.5	2	5.1
23. rules of lighting a fire in the forest	21	53.85	4	10.3	11	28.2
24. what to do to avoid a landslide	30	76.92	9	23.1	0	0
25. what to do at home during a landslide	18	46.15	3	7.7	11	28.2
26. characteristics of a landslide	18	46.15	7	17.9	11	28.2
27. what to do during a thunderstorm	25	64.10	1	2.6	12	30.8
28. what to do if a thunderstorm occurs while in an open space outdoors	26	66.67	7	17.9	3	7.7
29. what to do if in a building during a strong wind	12	30.77	2	5.1	21	53.8
30. how to act if outside during a strong wind	18	46.15	2	5.1	16	41

The result reveals that there were pupils who were able to show that they were aware and knowledgeable. It was also observed in the result that the pupils who were aware and knowledgeable were lower than the result on the individual summary of the level of awareness and level of knowledge. There were 2.6% to 79.5% who claimed that they were aware but did not get the correct answer except for the statements about the contents of emergency kit/bag and how to avoid a landslide.

Section 6. Significant Difference Between Knowledge and Awareness on DRRM

Table 9 shows the t-test for paired samples results on a significant difference between the knowledge and awareness on DRRM.

Table 9. Paired-Sample T-test Result on Significant Difference Between Knowledge and Awareness

		Mean	Level	N	Std. Deviation	Test statistic t(38) = -2.658, p = .011**
Pair 1	Knowledge	75.10	Knowledgeable	39	14.037	
	Awareness	85.21	Highly Aware	39	17.863	

*significant at 0.05

**significant at 0.01

There was a significant difference in the level of knowledge and awareness, $t(38)=-2.658, p=.011$. The awareness was significantly higher (85.21) than knowledge (75.10). This also means that not all who perceived that they were aware of DRRM were knowledgeable about it. This was supported by the result found in Table 8.

Knowledge or awareness may not be the only thing that matters because this does not dictate the Grade 6 pupils' ability to do action during the disaster. However, this can reduce the negative consequences of disasters (Smith, 1993; Mulyasari et al., 2011) and can help for their safety (Ahmad et al., 2017). Moreover, children are more vulnerable during these times (Merchant, 2015). Besides, improving the knowledge of the students may also influence the preparedness of the pupils based on the findings of the study of Sujarwo, Noorhamdani, and Fathoni (2018) and Hoffmann and Muttarak (2017).

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge and awareness of elementary pupils on the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Program. This study used a quantitative approach. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were computed to answer the research problems. The data were gathered using Google form. Based on the gathered data, the following is the summary of findings.

Summary of findings:

1. The Grade 6 pupils were knowledgeable on DRRM.
2. The Grade 6 pupils were highly aware of DRRM.
3. There was no significant difference between the mean ratings of the level of knowledge when the pupils are grouped by their sex.
4. There was no significant difference between the mean ratings of the level of awareness when the pupils are grouped by their sex.
5. There was no significant correlation between the mean scores on the level of knowledge and awareness on DRRM.
6. There was a significant difference between the mean ratings of the level of knowledge and skills on DRRM.

Conclusions:

Based on the findings, the following are concluded.

1. The Grade 6 pupils learned from their DRRM subjects.
2. The Grade 6 pupils' perception regarding their awareness of DRRM is very high.
3. The level of knowledge of male and female pupils is the same.
4. The level of awareness of male and female pupils is the same.
5. Level of knowledge and awareness are not associated with each other.
6. The Grade 6 pupils perceived that they were aware but not all of them were able to answer the corresponding item in the knowledge test correctly.

Recommendations:

1. The teachers and the whole DepEd to continue integrating the DRRM program.
2. The teachers exert more effort so that the Grade 6 pupils do not only perceive that they are aware but to be knowledgeable on what to do to prepare the pupils before, during, and after the disasters.
3. To give the same effort to both male and female pupils in teaching the DRRM.
4. To use the result of this study as a basis for the improvement of the DRRM program and enhancement or revision of the curriculum particularly on the subjects integrated with DRRM. It can also be a basis in crafting Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials for DRRM awareness intended for Grade 6 pupils.

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Project Timetable:

Activity	Duration	Start/Completion Dates
Full blown proposal	1 month	October 4, 2019
Data Gathering	1 month	October 24-November 24, 2019
Data Encoding	1 month	November 26–December 26, 2019
Data Analysis and Interpretation	3 months	-
Oral Presentation	-	-
Finalize full paper	-	-

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